

Energy-flexible operation of a cleaning machine through mathematical optimization

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Abstract

To promote renewable energy use and reduce the environmental impact of industrial facilities, we propose a novel demand response approach using aqueous parts cleaning machines. These machines offer high demand response potential due to their large water tanks, which can store thermal energy. A stochastic dynamic programming model is developed and integrated into a cyber-physical production system. It determines energy consumption for both the cleaning process and tank heating, using day-ahead electricity prices as a key decision variable. The model incorporates system constraints and controls tank temperature by switching heating elements on and off. An enhanced data model enables communication with the physical system. This work addresses the underexplored use of stochastic dynamic programming in systems with thermal storage. A case study shows that heating costs of the tanks were reduced by approximately 105 % using day-ahead prices and the proposed approach, while CO₂ emissions decreased by 8.6 %.

Keywords: Demand response; cyber-physical production system; optimal control; stochastic dynamic programming; single machine scheduling; inherent energy storage

APCM aqueous parts cleaning machine	MINLP mixed-integer nonlinear programming
ASU air separation unit	MILP mixed-integer linear programming
CPPS cyber-physical production system	MPC model predictive control
DR demand response	DP dynamic programming
DRM Design Research Methodology	SDP stochastic dynamic programming
EFDM Energy Flexibility Data Model	TPCM throughput cleaning machine
ENTSO-E European Network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity	VDI Association of German Engineers e.V.
EPEX European Power Exchange	JSON JavaScript Object Notation
LP linear programming	OPC UA Open Platform Communications Unified Architecture

1 Introduction

More than 80 % of the world's energy consumption comes from fossil fuels like petroleum, natural gas, and coal [1]. Expanding the use of renewable energy is one approach to decreasing reliance on fossil fuels [5]. Global renewable energy generation almost doubled

between 2011 and 2021, rising from 402 TW h to 763 TW h [1]. Transitioning to renewable electricity generation requires adjustments to the electricity system [2]. Since renewable energy sources naturally fluctuate, consumers must adjust to changes in supply, for example, by using energy storage systems and applying demand response (DR) strategies as part of demand-side integration [18].

In previous work, we analysed the DR potential of an industrial aqueous parts cleaning machine (APCM) [8]. Throughput cleaning machine (TPCM) is a specific type of APCM with continuous material flow. Building on this, we developed an automation data model designed to facilitate communication between DR services and machine automation, as demonstrated in [12]. To fully exploit this architecture, an optimization algorithm is necessary. In this paper, we propose a stochastic dynamic programming (SDP) approach for controlling the heating elements.

The paper is structured based on the Design Research Methodology (DRM) [3]. In section 2, literature describing DR for APCM as well as modeling and optimization of inherent storages is analyzed as descriptive study I. The prescriptive study starts with the clarification of the research objective in section 3 followed by the design (section 4) and implementation (section 5). The results are then analyzed and discussed in form of descriptive study II in section 6. Finally, a summary and outlook is drawn.

2 Literature

This section reviews the literature addressing the identified research gap, as part of descriptive study I. Fuhrländer-Völker et al. [9] implemented a mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) optimization algorithm on an APCM. In a field test power changes of up to 49 % and energy shifts of up to 82 % were achieved, demonstrating the high DR potential of such machines.

Regarding storage capacities in production context, the following optimization approaches have been implemented. Strobel et al. [22] present a general mathematical framework to assess the flexibility potential of inherent energy storage in industrial systems, demonstrated on a metalworking production line. The presented methodology enables inherent storages to be modeled. Zangenberg et al. [26] present a data-driven method for system identification of inherent thermal energy storages. Component-level modeling is used to enable model predictive control (MPC) for DR in the overall system. Applied to a cooling system using MILP, the method achieved a 10.06 % cost reduction and 4.93 % lower carbon emissions by adapting cooling demand to electricity price variations.

Extending the scope beyond discrete manufacturing to include other sectors such as the energy industry or the food industry, the following sources can be identified. Liu et al. [14] investigated a continuous stirred-tank reactor operated with dynamic production levels. Production was increased during low electricity prices, storing excess output, and reduced during high prices using stored material to meet demand. A dynamic programming (DP) approach was employed to minimize operating costs under time-of-use electricity pricing. Romero et al. [20] analyzed the operation of dewatering systems in underground mining environments. The study highlights that dewatering pumps exhibit operational flexibility, as they do not require continuous operation but can be temporally shifted within certain constraints. A MPC framework based on MILP was employed. The objective was to minimize the annualized total cost. Kelley et al. [11] examined the operation of an air separation unit (ASU). The study leverages the flexibility of the ASU by increasing production during periods of low electricity prices. The resulting overproduction is stored in dedicated tanks and can be retrieved later to meet demand. A linear programming (LP) approach was used to minimize operating costs. Wohlgenannt et al. [25] proposed a demand-side

management strategy for an industrial food processing facility, combining the building as a passive thermal storage with an actively chilled water storage. The optimization problem was formulated as a LP. MPC was applied to manage forecast uncertainties, with simulation results showing significant reductions in energy consumption, electricity costs, and peak load. The literature analysis has shown that MILP is frequently used in combination with MPC algorithms to address optimization problems in the context of DR. In contrast, the use of SDP in this field remains largely unexplored, revealing a clear research gap that this work seeks to address.

3 Conceptualization

In this section, the prescriptive study is carried out by presenting the conceptualization. This paper aims to implement and evaluate an SDP framework tailored to a TPCM, with the intention of ensuring methodological transferability to a broader range of APCM systems. The approach exploits the inherent storage capacity of the washing and rinsing tanks of the TPCM by actively utilizing the permissible temperature fluctuations, thereby enabling their integration into DR strategies. An appropriate SDP-based optimization is developed and demonstrated through a representative use case, including system modeling, parameterization, and automation integration. In the evaluation and discussion, we present results from a case study. The assessment is based on a defined set of metrics, primarily comparing the optimized energy costs with an unoptimized reference process (see section 5.3) as benchmark scenario.

4 Stochastic dynamic programming approach

The SDP approach is particularly well-suited to our problem. It involves sequential, history-dependent decisions at predefined time steps, whether to activate a certain number of heating elements or to allow passive cooling. During operation (see section 5.3), significant temperature fluctuations were observed, making accurate forecasting difficult and introducing considerable uncertainty into the system. These stochastic influences are modeled over their entire probability distribution, rather than being reduced to simple averages. The system is dynamic and subject to random influences. This structure is fully exploited by the SDP approach. The optimization problem is solved recursively using the *terminal cost function* V_n , which represents the expected cumulative costs from stage n to the end of the planning horizon. This yields the optimal policy δ^* . The recursion and its optimality properties have been thoroughly documented in the literature on dynamic programming (see, for example, [17]). While the problem can formally be reduced to a LP, such a transformation would result in a loss of the dynamic and stochastic structure [16]. An additional advantage of the SDP method lies in the one-time computation of the optimal policy, which can then be applied throughout the process. In contrast, MILP approaches, which have been widely used in the literature, are inherently static. They typically involve a large number of constraints, and the presence of integer variables significantly increases computational complexity [16].

5 Implementation

The previous described approach is now demonstrated on an TPCM.

5.1 System description, Automation structure and data model

This case study examines the cleaning of gearbox guide discs contaminated with cutting oil, using a TPCM from BvL Oberflächentechnik GmbH [7]. The process features aqueous detergent cleaning with continuous material flow, followed by convective drying. Cleaning

and rinsing are carried out using an aqueous detergent stored in two 500 L tanks. Each tank is equipped with five individually controllable electric heating elements, each rated at 6 kW. These heaters account for the largest share of the machine’s total average connected load of 96 kW, making them a key target for energy flexibility measures. In addition, the tanks are connected to the thermal network via a heat exchanger, enabling bivalent operation. Due to their thermal inertia, the heated detergent tanks offer significant DR potential as inherent thermal storage [22]. This enables the implementation of the DR measure *store energy (inherently)*, which is classified as an energy flexibility measure according to Association of German Engineers e.V. (VDI) 5207, under the assumption that the process is not adversely affected. In contrast, other flexibility strategies, such as *interrupting the process* or *adjusting operational parameters*, are not applicable in this case, since the material flow is continuous and must remain uninterrupted, and the process parameters are fixed to ensure operational reliability [23]. This assumption was made in consultation with industrial cleaning experts, as it can be reasonably expected, based on the principles of Sinner’s Circle, that a higher cleaning temperature is more likely to improve rather than impair the cleaning performance [19].

The day-ahead prices are retrieved via an API from the European Network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity (ENTSO-E) database. The optimizer is implemented in Python. The architecture structure follows the design of the eta-nexus package [21], which is based on developments from the eta-utility package [10]. It connects the standardized Open Platform Communications Unified Architecture (OPC UA) interface with the machine’s PLC. The interface is essential for implementing energy flexibility measures on the TPCM. It contains Energy Flexibility Data Model (EFDm) key figures, which provide a unified model for flexibility description [4], enabling standardized optimisation of flexible loads via unique identifiers.

5.2 Modeling

In the following section, the SDP approach is applied to our specific use case, and the relevant quantities are defined as follows [16, 24].

- (i) The *planning horizon* is defined by the total shift duration J and the time interval between decision stages $\Delta\tau$, yielding a total of N stages. These stages are traversed sequentially in descending order: $N, N-1, \dots, 1$.
- (ii) The *state space* \mathcal{S} comprises the feasible tank temperature levels, represented as a finite set of discretized values with step size $\lambda > 0$. It is divided into three subsets:

$$\mathcal{S} = \mathcal{S}_{\min}^< \cup \mathcal{S}_{\text{adm}} \cup \mathcal{S}_{\max}^>$$

where $\mathcal{S}_{\text{adm}} = \{T_{\min}, T_{\min} + \lambda, \dots, T_{\max}\}$ denotes the admissible range, in which the machine is intended to operate, $\mathcal{S}_{\min}^< = \{T_{\text{LB}}, \dots, T_{\min} - \lambda\}$ the lower inadmissible region, and $\mathcal{S}_{\max}^> = \{T_{\max} + \lambda, \dots, T_{\text{UB}}\}$ the upper inadmissible region. The bounds T_{LB} and T_{UB} denote the extreme temperatures that can be reached in a single stage under maximum cooling or heating, respectively.

- (iii) The *action space* $\mathcal{A} = \{0, 1, \dots, 5\}$ defines all possible actions, including cooling ($a = 0$) and heating with a heating elements for $a > 0$. Not all of these actions are admissible in every state; admissibility depends on the current temperature level. In inadmissible regions, only specific actions are permitted, heating in the lower zone and cooling in the upper zone. The resulting state-dependent admissible action set $\mathcal{D}(T)$ is defined as follows:

$$\mathcal{D}(T) = \begin{cases} \{1, \dots, 5\} & , T \in \mathcal{S}_{\min}^< \\ \mathcal{A} & , T \in \mathcal{S}_{\text{adm}} \\ \{0\} & , T \in \mathcal{S}_{\max}^> \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

(iv) Cooling dynamics are modeled by a discrete random variable \mathbf{W} with values $0 < w_1 < \dots < w_l \leq 1$ and probabilities $\eta_i = P(\mathbf{W} = w_i)$. Heating increments are described by \mathbf{X} supported on $\mathcal{X} = \{x_{\min}, \dots, x_{\max}\}$, with state- and action-dependent probabilities $q_{T,a}(x) = P_{T,a}(\mathbf{X} = x), x \in \mathcal{X}$.

(v) The transition probabilities $p_{T,a}(T')$ from state T to T' under action a are:

$$p_{T,0}(T') = \sum_{i=0}^l \eta_i \mathbf{1}_{\{T'\}}(\lfloor (1-w_i)\vartheta_{HW} + w_i T \rfloor_\lambda) \quad (2)$$

for cooling ($a = 0$), where ϑ_{HW} denotes the temperature at the housing wall, and

$$p_{T,a}(T') = \begin{cases} q_{T,a}(T' - T) & , \text{if } T' - T \in \mathcal{X} \\ 0 & , \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

for heating ($a > 0$).

(vi) Known day-ahead prices ρ_n and heating costs $r_{\text{HC},n}(a) = L(a)\rho_n$ are incorporated, where $L(a)$ denotes energy consumption for action a .

(vii) The penalty costs r_{PC} are imposed when the system leaves the admissible temperature range, calculated proportionally to the deviation from T_{\min} or T_{\max} , using coefficients $c_{\min}^<$ and $c_{\max}^>$, respectively. For cooling, they are given by

$$r_{\text{PC}}(T, 0) = c_{\min}^< \sum_{i=0}^l \eta_i \max\{0, T_{\min} - ((1-w_i)\vartheta_{HW} + w_i T)\} \quad (4)$$

and for heating by

$$r_{\text{PC}}(T, a) = c_{\min}^< \sum_{x \in \mathcal{X}} q_{T,a} \max\{0, T_{\min} - (T+x)\} + c_{\max}^> \sum_{x \in \mathcal{X}} q_{T,a} \max\{0, (T+x) - T_{\max}\} \quad (5)$$

(viii) Stage costs r_N combine penalty and heating costs:

$$r_n(T, a) = \begin{cases} r_{\text{PC}}(T, 0) & , a = 0, \quad T \in \mathcal{S} \setminus \mathcal{S}_{\min}^< \\ r_{\text{HC},n}(a) + r_{\text{PC}}(T, a) & , a \in \{1, \dots, 5\}, \quad T \in \mathcal{S} \setminus \mathcal{S}_{\max}^> \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

(ix) The terminal cost function V_0 is zero. For stages $n = N, \dots, 1$, V_n is computed recursively by:

$$V_n(T_n) = \min \left\{ r_n(T_n, 0) + \sum_{i=1}^l \eta_i V_{n-1} ([(1 - w_i) \vartheta_{HW} + w_i T_n]_\lambda), \right. \\ \left. \min_{a \in \mathcal{A} \setminus \{0\}} \left\{ r_n(T_n, a) + \sum_{x \in \mathcal{X}} q_{T_n, a}(x) V_{n-1}(T_n + x) \right\} \right\} \quad (7)$$

Figure 1: Illustration of the transition probabilities for heating with a heating elements at temperature T

5.3 Parameterization

A full shift consists of eight hours, but the shift duration for the experiment was set to four hours to reduce experimental effort. To ensure system safety, control actions must be executed every three minutes, resulting in a total of 80 decision stages. To ensure system safety, control actions must be executed every three minutes, resulting in a total of 80 decision stages. The admissible temperature range was defined between 48°C and 70°C . The lower limit reflects the two-point control of the reference process (48°C to 52°C around a 50°C setpoint), while the upper limit corresponds to the machine's maximum allowable temperature specified by the manufacturer. A discretization parameter of $\lambda = 0.1^\circ\text{C}$ was chosen to match the resolution of the temperature sensor.

To identify the heating and cooling parameters of the tank, cleaning experiments were conducted using the same parts and settings as in the reference process, which was developed in the preceding project Lotus [15, S. 34]. The number of active heating elements was systematically varied. Heating was applied from T_{\min} to T_{\max} , while cooling occurred passively in the reverse direction. The parameters were estimated using linear regression, and the associated uncertainty was quantified based on the regression residuals.

6 Evaluation and Discussion

Within the scope of descriptive study II, the evaluation is carried out to demonstrate the functionality of the optimizer. To this end, the described SDP approach is implemented on

Figure 2: Power of the tank heating elements (top), temperatures of tanks (center), and day-ahead electricity prices (bottom) for the optimized process

the actual TPCM system at the ETA Research Factory to demonstrate its practical applicability. For electricity pricing, we use European Power Exchange (EPEX) Spot day-ahead market prices from May 31, 2025, between 15:00 and 19:00 for the Germany-Luxembourg bidding zone [6]. The date was selected as a random day in May.

Figure 2 presents the results of the field tests. Electricity prices were lower at the beginning of the shift and increased towards the end. Notably, prices were negative between 15:30 and 16:00 as well as between 16:30 and 16:45. During the early phase of the shift, heating was primarily performed when electricity prices were negative. In these periods, all heating elements were activated to take full advantage of the cost benefit. Towards the end of the shift, heating occurred only when necessary or during brief periods of favorable pricing. Compared to the rinse tank, the wash tank was heated more intensively at the beginning of the shift and only minimally towards the end. This strategy leverages its favorable thermal properties: the wash tank cools down more slowly and can be reheated more quickly. As a result, it acts as a thermal buffer, enabling the system to better bridge periods of high electricity prices later in the shift. Compared to the reference process [15, S. 34], the heating elements exhibit longer activation periods and primarily operate when electricity prices are low. As a result, the tank temperature fluctuates in a wider temperature range compared to the reference process but consistently satisfies the specified temperature bounds throughout the experiment. In the reference process, heating costs were 12.16 € with static electricity tariffs of 210 €/MWh and 3.27 € with day-ahead prices. The proposed SDP approach reduced costs to -0.17 €, which corresponds to a cost reduction of 105 % compared to the reference process with day-ahead prices and 101 % compared to static tariffs. CO₂ emissions decreased from 11.2 kg to 10.2 kg, a reduction of 8.60 %.

Due to the complexity of parameterizing the system, a linear approximation of the heating behavior is employed. Additionally, external disturbances are often correlated, complicating their accurate estimation. While the uncertainty associated with the tank system is

represented relatively well, the overall computational complexity, though currently manageable, could become a limiting factor in larger-scale applications. Generalizing the approach to more extensive, integrated systems remains difficult due to increased complexity. Furthermore, longer experimental runs are required to account for heating phases and shift transitions, which can significantly impact system behavior and energy consumption.

7 Conclusion

In this work, we present a detailed SDP model for a DR service. The system uses a TPCM to implement energy flexibility measures. The model accounts for uncertainties, allowing precise adaptation and demonstrating significant savings compared to the reference process. We validate the model in a field test involving a thermally process-controlled TPCM and show that the DR measures effectively controls the machine in response to fluctuating electricity prices. For future work, it would be advisable to incorporate both the option of bivalence and the drying module of the TPCM as additional flexible components within the optimization algorithm. Furthermore, additional control variables, such as product quality, should be taken into account in order to avoid negative implications for the process. The implementation of a multi-objective optimization approach could also prove beneficial in systematically addressing potential trade-offs between economic and qualitative performance indicators. In addition, extended tests on selected representative days would be advisable to demonstrate the applicability of the optimizer for industrial use.

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